

at 25- × 25-cm spacing. All P, K, and Zn were applied at last puddling. Nitrogen was applied according to a schedule to single plots on each farm (Table 1).

Rice yield (t/ha) from each treatment was recorded at 14% moisture. Results from experiments conducted during each year and pooled data were subjected to statistical analysis using randomized complete block design (Table 2). Each farm was considered to be a block.

Rice yield increased significantly due to fertilizer application. Although fertilizer treatments were statistically at par, three splits appeared to be more

Table 2. Average yield (t/ha) of Basmati 385 as affected by split application of N in farmers' fields, Punjab, Pakistan, 1990-92.^a

Treatment (no.)	1990 (5 ^b)	1991 (3 ^b)	1992 (4 ^b)	Pooled (12 ^b)	Increase over control (%)	Range of variation
1	2.4 b	2.6 b	2.5 b	2.5 b		2.0 - 3.1
2	4.1 a	3.9 a	3.9 a	4.0 a	59	2.9 - 4.6
3	4.3 a	4.0 a	4.0 a	4.1 a	66	3.1 - 4.8
4	4.2 a	4.0 a	3.9 a	4.1 a	65	3.1 - 4.6

The block effect is significant.

^aFigures followed by a common letter are nonsignificant at 0.05 LSD. ^bNo. of farms.

efficient for rice production. Farmers can realize more benefits from money spent on N fertilizer if they can afford the

additional laborer to apply the N in splits. ■

Grain yield and ¹⁵N uptake of drill-seeded rice as affected by coated calcium carbide

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In drill-seeded rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) production systems in the United States, permanent flooding is usually imposed about 4 wk after drilling of rice seeds. Fertilizer N is usually applied just prior to flooding, and topdressings are later applied from an airplane. Losses of fertilizer N through nitrification and denitrification reactions in these systems have not been well-characterized. If these losses are significant, then use of a nitrification inhibitor to reduce nitrifica-

tion-denitrification may have potential as an N management tool. Coated calcium carbide (CCC) is a slow-release source of acetylene, a potent nitrification inhibitor, that is formed when calcium carbide (CaC₂) is wetted.

In a 2-yr field study, the effect of CCC on uptake of ¹⁵N-labeled urea, dry matter production (first year only), and grain yield (both years) of drill-seeded flooded rice was tested. The long-grained semidwarf rice variety, Lemont, was drill-seeded in late April 1990 and 1991 at 112 kg/ha. Approximately 29.5 kg P/ha and 55.6 kg K/ha were banded 5 cm deep at seeding. The experiment was laid out as a two-way factorial (urea treatment and N rate) in four randomized complete blocks. Immediately before the experimental site was permanently flooded 4 wk after seeding, urea N fertilizer treatments at 60 and 120 kg N/ha were surface-applied as urea alone and as urea + CCC at 20 kg CaC₂/ha. In the first year, 5 atom% ¹⁵N urea was applied at the 120 kg N/ha rate in microplots estab-

lished beside the large plots. A control was untreated.

Grain yield responded positively (P<0.05) to N rate in both years (see table). An increase in grain yield with urea + CCC vs urea alone was only observed in 1990 at the highest N rate (P<0.05). Addition of CCC to urea in 1990 resulted in small but significant (P<0.05) increases in fertilizer-derived N (¹⁵N) uptake and dry matter production between 3 and 6 wk after fertilization compared with urea alone. This might suggest that nitrification-denitrification losses were a factor in the first year.

A lack of response to CCC in the second year might have been related to a change in the coatings of the experimental CCC used. The coating material used in CCC is a mixture of waxes and shellac, applied in several layers. In preparing the CCC for the second year, more coatings were applied with the expectation that the release of acetylene would last longer. At the end of the season, however, much of the CCC applied was found on the soil, unreacted, indicating that the coatings were too thick. Improvement of the coatings is needed to give a more consistent release of acetylene so that CCC can be further tested in flooded rice. ■

Effect of coated calcium carbide (CCC) and N rate on grain yield (t/ha) of dry seeded rice.^a Crowley, Louisiana, USA, 1990-91.

Urea treatment	1990			1991		
	0	60	120	0	60	120
		(kg N/W)			(kg N/W)	
Urea	5.6	6.8 a	6.6 b	3.5 a	5.1 a	6.6 a
Urea + CCC	-	7.2 a	7.6 a	3.5 a	4.9 a	6.3 a

^aMeans in a column followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% probability level by F-test.